

Effective Use of Classroom Management Techniques in Overcrowded Classrooms

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Abstract

This study was conducted to find the effective use of classroom management techniques in overcrowded classroom. It also explored factors that influence overcrowded classrooms.

Key Words

Effective, Classroom
Management, Techniques,
Overcrowded

30 secondary school teachers participated in the study. A questionnaire and a check list were used for the collection of the data. The findings indicated that teachers used different management techniques in the overcrowded classrooms.

Introduction

Classroom management is an approach in which a teacher controls student behavior and interaction. With it, teaching is most effective. It affects educational objectives and decides a set of moral and behavioral norms for them.

Teachers frequently used the term management with reference to the process during which lessons are not disturbed by students' behavior. Rose and Gallup (2005) have reflected that the commonest request for support from teachers is associated with classroom management and behaviour.

Effective strategies on part of the teachers invite students' attention as well as their involvement in the classroom because teaching and learning co-respond with each other. Planning instructions makes instructions fruitful and students are satisfied with the environment. Management is all about teachers and students and influences their behavior. Marzono (2003, 2007) augmented that the significance related to feeling safe at school is connected to the study of education and its management in classrooms. Deprived of this sentimentality security, understudies will create nervousness and get to be uneasy in the classroom.

Churchward (2009), "There are numerous specialists letting us know in what way to knob discipline matters in our classrooms.

Brannon (2010) has argued that in spite of the fact that exploration exhibits the implication of classroom management, it is unclear which technique or procedure is more proper to utilize in primary schools. The interactionist utilizes a common classroom administration methodology (Glasser, 1997) or fosters standby results by embracing a mix of interventionist and noninterventionist approaches as discussed by Lanoue (2009).

It can be truly stated that classroom management and classroom administration has focused on the establishment of behavioral and instructional administration in teaching learning ecology. McArthur (2002) demonstrated that teachers have long comprehended that issues can influence the classroom environment. Rosas and West (2009) stated, "Classroom administration is a reasonable sympathy toward instructors, especially given the way that schools are required to give a sheltered, systematic learning ecology and that educators are accountable for understudies' scholastic undertakings".

Kizlik (2009) remarked on the significance of utilizing proper viable commendation versus inadequate recognition. One ought to screen their applause to guarantee needed practices (Kizlik, 2009). Generally, the Wong's prescribe that instructors build up systems and show them to understudies utilizing an approach comprising of three stages (Wong and Wong, 1998). It can be deduced that they entrusted that the educator is on task the moment the understudies enter the classroom. Wong's convictions about the classroom are more centered on educational modules as per White (2006).

Classroom administration undertakes an imperative part in understudies learning encounters. They support understudies' scholarly aptitudes and capacities and in addition their social advancement. (Bosch, 2006). As indicated by Evert child and Harris "classroom administration has been changed from order hones and behavioral obstructions to serving as a more finish descriptor of instructors' engagements in constituting learning circumstances and building group "Foutz (2005) says, "Actual classroom management commences with the teacher. The teacher must design well so that the students will be capable to come across their education and performance objectives. Mayeski (2005) argued that it is very significant for the teachers to generate safe and settled situation in the classroom to increase the learning environment for students. In this regard the part of the teacher as leader is also very critical. Referring to this point, Ramsey (1999) stated that the role of an effective leader is to create a climate that welcomes, supports, and rewards innovative thinking and problem solving. Shah and Inamullah (2012) also observed that stuffed classroom affects students learning .It also affects teachers and behavioral problems occur during such situations.

University of Nebraska (2005) has given sources for classroom arrangement as:

1. Seating arrangements of the students should be in a proper way so that the students can easily see chalkboards, screens, presentations and displays and the educators and pupils can easily move in the classroom.
2. The place of the teacher should be in front of the room
3. Classroom instructions should be clear to all the students.

Salem-al-amarat (2011) carried out a research about problems of teachers of private schools. He was of the view that classroom problems are serious such as parents, teacher's breakage of property, no educational facilities and not proper environment etc. Results of the study illustrates that statistically there were less difficulties interrelated to classroom environment but more problems are associated to behavior because different variables coordinate with each other which causes disturbances in educational development.

Nemrah (2006) quoted that teachers had to compact with different students in the classroom, having different problems and they need much more time to handle such students

Simonsen (2008) investigated that as it may, more efficient methodologies utilizing meta-investigation are expected to decide the size of the impacts of classroom administration. In any case, earlier research amalgamations on mediations focusing on solitary conduct have inspected school-based projects all in all instead of classroom-based conduct administration.

A meta-investigation by D. Wilson, Gottfredson, and Najaka (2001) analyzed the impacts of school-based anticipation of wrongdoing, substance use, dropout, nonattendance, and other behavior issues. A wide assortment of intercessions was considered in that study, including singular directing, conduct adjustment, and more extensive school techniques, for example, natural changes or changes to instructional practice. The authors' examination discovered contrasts in impacts in view of kind of mediation, with intellectual behavioral methodologies indicating bigger impacts than non-subjective behavioral guiding or other remedial interventions. Since the incorporation criteria were sufficiently wide to cover any school-based intervention, it was past the extent of classroom-based, educator executed mediations. Wilson and partners (2003) discovered comparative impacts for school-construct counteractive action programs with respect to issue conduct. In any case, about the greater part of the studies were show extends instead of routine practice programs executed in average school-based situations. Successful mediations should be tried in run of the mill school-based locales to further shore up their levels of confirmation (U.S. Division of Education Institute of Education Sciences National Center for Educational Evaluation and Regional Assistance, 2003). Another meta-investigation by S. Wilson and Lipsey (2006) inspected school-based projects that focused on social data preparing and discovered abatements in forceful and troublesome conduct for understudies in treatment conditions.

Research Objectives

1. To classify the classroom management techniques.
2. To explore the factors affecting management in overcrowded classroom.

Significance of the Study

This study may be noteworthy for the pre service and in services teachers and may be helpful for teachers of elementary and secondary schools in respect with classroom management, in the large size classroom. It will also provide guide line for overcrowded classroom to manage, because teachers face many problems in large classroom and the present study may help them to manage such classrooms with effective techniques.

Sample

Out of forty secondary teachers twenty-six teachers were selected as sample of the study using simple random sampling technique. For researcher’s classroom observation, ten teachers were further short listed.

Research Instrument

Questionnaire for Teachers

A self- developed questionnaire was used as data collection tool from the Secondary School teachers in order to obtain the responses of the teacher about the effective use of classroom management techniques in the overcrowded classrooms. The questionnaire comprised of twenty statements. First section of this instrument extracted personal information of respondents whereas the second section consisted of close ended statements related to objectives of the study. Likert scale value of 4 was assigned to always, 3 to often, 2 to seldom, 1 to some extent and 0 to not at all.

A Check list for Researchers’ Classroom Observation

A self- constructed checklist was used to conduct classroom observations when teachers were teaching in overcrowded classes. This checklist was constructed to carry in depth observations about effective classroom management techniques being used by teachers in the overcrowded classrooms. The check list also provided quantitative evidence about the solicitation of effective classroom management skills.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher administered the data collection tool personally and the respondents cooperated in this regard. Classroom observation was conceded to observe the teachers during teaching- learning transaction in the classroom. For this purpose, ten teachers teaching at secondary level were taken into consideration for class room observation. All teachers were observed for the period of thirty minutes.

Data Analysis

Percentage, Mean and chi square were used as statistical tool for the analysis of the data. The study considered Chi-square because it is the one commonly used by researchers in comparison to the other non-parametric tests. (Kothari, 2007).

Table 1. Proper Seating Arrangement

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	15	8	2	0	0	8.8
Classroom observation		Yes 10		No 0		10

Table 1 shows that the means score for statement “The seats are properly arranged in the classroom” is (24) always, (1) often, (0) seldom, (0) to some extent and (0) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (10). Means score (8.8) of teachers opinions is less than means score (10) of observation for this statement.

Table 2. Effective Classroom Management is Significant

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	24	1	0	0	0	9.9
Classroom observation		Yes 4		No 0		4

Table 2 shows that the means score for statement “Effective classroom management is important” is (9.9) with (24) always, (1) often, (0) seldom, (0) to some extent and (0) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas

means score for observation is (4). Means score (9.9) of teachers' opinions is greater than means score (7) of observation for this statement.

Table 3. Classroom environment have a good effect on teachers and students

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	22	3	0	0	0	9.7
Classroom observation		Yes 7		No 0		7

Table 3 shows that the means score for statement “Classroom environment have a good effect on teachers and students” is (9.7) with (22) always, (3) often, (0) seldom, (0) to some extent and (0) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (7). Means score (9.7) of teachers opinions is greater than means score (7) of observation for this statement.

Table 4. The teacher involves students in the design/formulation of classroom rules and procedures”

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	6	14	4	1	0	7.5
Classroom observation		Yes 4		No 0		4

Table 4 shows that the means score for statement “The teacher involves students in the design/formulation of classroom rules and procedures” is (7.5) with (6) always, (14) often, (4) seldom, (1) to some extent and (0) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (4). Means score (7.5) of teachers opinions is greater than means score (4) of observation for this statement

Table 5. Effective Classroom Management can Improve Student’s Achievement

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	17	7	1	0	0	9.1
Classroom observation		Yes 9	No 0			9

Table 5 shows that the means score for statement “Effective classroom management can improve student’s achievement” is (9.1) with (17) always, (7) often, (1) seldom, (0) to some extent and (0) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (9). Means score (9.1) of teachers opinions is greater than means score (9) of observation for this statement.

Table 6. The teacher involves students in the design/formulation of classroom rule and Procedure

0\Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	12	10	1	2	0	8.2
Classroom observation		Yes 8		No 0		8

Table 6 shows that the means score for statement “The teacher involves students in the design/formulation of classroom rules and procedures” is (8.2) with (12) always, (10) often, (1) seldom, (2) to some extent and (0) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (8). Means score (8.2) of teachers opinions is greater than means score (8) of observation for this statement.

Table 7. Permanent and effective learning can be ensured Through Effective

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	7	4	8	3	0	8.8
Classroom observation		Yes 1		No 0		1

Table 7 shows that the means score for statement “Permanent and effective learning can be ensured through effective is (8.8) with (7) always, (4) often, (8) seldom, (3) to some extent and (3) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (0). Means score (5.9) of teachers opinions is less than means score (9) of observation for this statement.

Table 8. Each Student is different as an Individual in the Class

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	14	6	4	1	0	8.3
Classroom observation		Yes 2		No 0		2

Table 8 shows that the means score for statement “Each student is different as an individual in the class.” is (8.3) with (14) always, (6) often, (4) seldom, (1) to some extent and (0) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (2). Means score (8.3) of teachers opinions is greater than means score (2) of observation for this statement.

Table 9. It is not important to involve students in the design of Classroom Rules and Procedure

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	7	4	8	3	0	8.8
Classroom observation		Yes 1		No 0		1

Table 9 shows that the means score for statement “It is not important to involve students in the design of classroom rules and procedures” is (8.8) with (7) always, (4) often, (8) seldom, (3) to some extent and (3) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (0). Means score (8.8) of teachers opinions is less than means score (9) of observation for this statement.

Table 10. Teacher Provides a Sense of Security to the Student

Category	Always	Often	Seldom	To some extent	Not at all	Mean score
Teacher perception	7	4	8	3	3	5.9
Classroom observation		Yes 9		No 0		9

Table 10 shows that the means score for statement “Teacher provides a sense of security to the student” is (5.9) with (7) always, (4) often, (8) seldom, (3) to some extent and (3) not at all of teachers opinions for these options, whereas means score for observation is (9). Means score (5.9) of teachers opinions is less than means score (9) of observation for this statement.

Discussion

A successful classroom atmosphere is positively dependent upon classroom management skills of effective teachers. Effective classroom management needs a set of comprehensive measures for increasing student curiosity and stimulating students towards learning. It is obvious from the literary research works that classroom activities, school rules and procedures, student behaviour and routines, room and seating arrangement as well as parent involvement are all decisive factors of upright classroom management.

Results indicated that student seats in the classroom are properly arranged, teachers are effectively using classroom management skills and most of the teachers involve students in formulation of classroom rules and procedures. There is a need that the teachers should involve the students in the teaching learning refresher course should be organized to train the teachers in the area of teaching techniques

Rogers and Freiberg (1994) have also indicated that classroom administration can profoundly affect learning. Behavioral classroom administration and instructional classroom administration are thought to be segments of compelling instructional practices (Kraft, 2010; Martin and Sass 2010; Marzano and Marzano, 2003; Wolfgang and Glickman, 1980). Quality educators have a variety of individual attributes that effects their instructional practices as well. It is basic that classroom conduct is overseen so that understudy accomplishment can happen. This investigation of classroom administration and its effect on understudy accomplishment will be helpful in "a period when examination lets us know that instructors are likely the absolute most imperative component that we can do much about" (Marzano, et al., 2003, p.1). This study was intended to answer imperative inquiries numerous instructors are asking, as classroom administration turns into a 20 progressively critical methodology towards giving a learning situation in which no youngster is abandoned

Conclusions

1. Majority of the teachers effectively use classroom management skills, but researcher's classroom pointed out the weakness of the teachers in this skill.
2. It was illustrated that teachers they involved students in formulation of classroom rules and procedures, but researchers' classroom observation did not support this claim.
3. It was demonstrated that teachers provide a sense of security to the students, but classroom observation negated this claim.
4. It was illustrated that classroom management techniques have good effect on the student learning and researcher's classroom observation also supported this claim.
5. It was demonstrated that classroom management techniques have good effect on the student learning and researcher's classroom observation also supported this claim.
6. It was illustrated that teachers focused on the positive aspect of learning during the class, but researcher's classroom observation did not support this claim.
7. It was concluded that teacher is able to establish healthy associations with the students and researcher's observation also showed that the teachers tended to do so.
8. It was concluded that Audio visual aids are available in the classroom and researcher's classroom observation also supported this claim.

Recommendations

1. While teachers highlighted that teachers planned the lesson before going to classroom but classroom observation did not prove this claim. Thus, it is suggested that more importance may be laid on developing effective lesson planning skills during trainings.
2. Teachers may be provided skillful training in the domain of classroom discipline and management. They claimed to involve the students in the teaching learning process, but researcher's classroom observation indicate that they did not do so. It is recommended that refresher courses may be organized to train the teachers in the area of teaching techniques and classroom management.
3. Audio visual aids are available in the classroom but are not properly used in the classrooms it is recommended that the teachers may be encouraged to use audio visual aids for making teaching and learning effective.
4. It is recommended that similar studies may be conducted across different geographic regions and at all educational levels so that a variety of findings may be deduced for further recommendations about improvement in classroom management.

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